

Figure S1. Transmission electron micrographs of cultured *L. erythrorhizon* cells fixed with the HPF/FS method. Enlarged parts of a cell in (a) are indicated with white squares (b - d). Panels (e, f) are of different cells from (a), showing frequently seen bunches of characteristic extracellular structures. Panels (g) and (h) highlight small electron-dense particles inside the cell walls, in which cultured cells were treated with 5 mM aluminum chloride before fixation to fix shikonin derivatives. CW, cell wall. Scale bars are: a, 2 mm; b, d, e, 500 nm; c, g, h, 200 nm; f, 1 mm.

Figure S2. Relative signal intensity of each lipid class in lipidomic analysis of *L. erythrorhizon* cultured cells. The values of fraction in LS Dark cells (shikoinn-non-producing) were set to 1 for each lipid class. Black dots represent individual values of each repeat (n = 3; LS Dark, n = 4; M9 Dark and M9 Light). PC, phosphatidylcholine; lysoPC, lysophosphatidylcholine; PE, phosphatidylethanolamine; lysoPE, lysophosphatidylethanolamine; PG, phosphatidylglycerol; PI, phosphatidylinositol; SQDG, sulfoquinovosyldiacylglycerol; MGDG, monogalactosyldiacylglycerol; DGDG, digalactosyldiacylglycerol.

Fig. S3. Subcellular localization of LePGT expressed in *N. benthamiana* epidermal cells. Confocal microscopic images of LePGT1-mGFP (A), LePGT2-mGFP (B), and GFP-h (C) transiently expressed in epidermal cells of *N. benthamiana* leaves by agroinfiltration. Bars = 10 μm

Fig. S4. Normal phase thin-layer chromatography (TLC) analysis of lipid fraction from *L. erythrorhizon* cells cultured in M9. The TLC was developed with n-hexane: diethyl ether (6 : 4, v/v). (Left) Without staining, with shikonin derivatives appearing as red spots; (right) following staining with I₂ vapor after separation, showing TAG spots. Shikonin derivatives identified in standard specimens are also indicated on the right.

primuline staining

Fig. S5. Normal phase thin-layer chromatography (TLC) analysis of lipids extracted from hairy roots of *L. erythrorhizon*. The TLC was developed with n-hexane: diethyl ether (7: 3, v/v). (Left) Without staining; (right) after staining with 80% (v/v) aqueous acetone containing 0.01% (w/v) primuline. Yellow arrowheads indicate TAG spots.

Supplemental Table 1. Primers used for LePGT2 gene construction.

purpose for use	gene/vector	sequence
cloning of LePGT2 using In-fusion reaction	LePGT2	Fw: GCAGGCTCCGCGGCCGCCACCATGA G TTC CAAACAAACACAGCTAAAGAA
		Rv: AGCTGGGTCGGCGCGCCCAGGAAAC AATC TCCCAACTAAGATGC
linearizing pENTR/D-TOPO	pENTR/D-TOPO	Fw: CGCGCCGACCCAGCTTTCTTGTACAA AGTT
		Rv: GGCCGCGGAGCCTGCTTTTTTTGTACA AAGT